

REFORMS FOR PROMOTING CLOSER COOPERATION WITH THE PUBLIC THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MORAL AND EDUCATIONAL QUALITIES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS PERSONNEL

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Abstract. *Moral and educational work is a systematic process aimed at enhancing the inner world, moral values, legal culture, and civic outlook of personnel. Its primary goal is to educate individuals to be morally mature and knowledgeable, strengthen the moral environment in society, foster love for the homeland and loyalty to the people among youth, ensure social and moral stability, and cultivate high moral standards and patriotism among personnel. This also includes promoting respect for national and universal values, preventing corruption, abuse, and indiscipline, and improving public engagement skills. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-10, dated January 20, 2023, “On Additional Measures to Transform Internal Affairs Bodies into a People-Oriented Professional Structure and Promote Closer Cooperation with the Population,” the “Code of Professional Culture and Service Discipline of Internal Affairs Personnel” was approved. This document establishes requirements for the conduct, ethics, and discipline of internal affairs officers and cadets, as well as students of the Ministry of Internal Affairs educational institutions, both during official duties and in extracurricular activities. It regulates relations between superiors and subordinates and sets rules for incentives and disciplinary measures. However, the ethical and disciplinary requirements for heads and military personnel of internal affairs military units, as well as their mutual relations and application of incentives or disciplinary measures, are governed by the Discipline Charter of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For civilian personnel of internal affairs bodies, these matters are regulated by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan governing labor relations.*

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Introduction

The rules and requirements established in the Code aim to ensure that personnel approach their official duties honestly, conscientiously, and with a deep sense of responsibility and initiative, instilling high moral and ethical standards, patriotism, and professional dedication. They are also designed to prevent improper conduct, abuse, and corruption at an early stage. Every officer is required to know and strictly comply with the Code from the day of employment until the end of service, regardless of position or job function. Compliance with the Code is one of the primary criteria for evaluating professional effectiveness and service discipline. Personal interests or other subjective reasons cannot justify violations of the legislation or the provisions of the Code.

Rules of Professional Culture for Internal Affairs Personnel

The rules of professional culture apply to all personnel, regardless of their position, and define the main requirements and standards for ethical conduct and professional behavior. Personnel serving in the internal affairs system are required to adhere to the following key standards of professional culture:

- Be polite, modest, and calm when interacting with citizens; avoid any discrimination or preferential treatment based on social background, economic status, or other factors.
- Respect the customs and traditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other nations; consider the cultural and other characteristics of different ethnic, social, and religious groups; contribute to social stability and interethnic and interfaith harmony.
- Examine and respond to the requests of individuals and legal entities fully, impartially, and promptly, in accordance with the law.
- Avoid any actions that might cause citizens to doubt the conscientious performance of duties or negatively affect the reputation of internal affairs bodies; avoid creating conflict situations.
- While performing official duties, do not discriminate against citizens or other individuals and take their rights, freedoms, and lawful interests into account.
- Avoid any actions (or inaction) that could interfere with fulfilling service obligations or create conflicts of interest, whether personal, financial, or otherwise.
- Prevent favoritism, nepotism, localism, or any other negative behaviors in the execution of official duties.
- Show respect to representatives of official media when informing the public about internal affairs activities and assist them in obtaining accurate information according to established procedures.
- Perform official duties conscientiously, honestly, and professionally, avoiding formalism, fraud, and abuse.
- Strictly follow internal regulations, telephone etiquette, and standards of dress and appearance.
- Do not discuss the activities of state bodies or officials on social media, avoid immoral language, and refrain from posting biased or subjective materials that could undermine public trust or confidence in reforms, including those within internal affairs bodies.
- Use service premises, state property, technical equipment, and other internal affairs resources solely for official purposes.

Anti-Corruption Measures:

Personnel must actively combat all forms of corruption and contribute to its prevention. They are required to report to their superior or the competent authority any situation in which they are encouraged by others to commit illegal acts, as well as any known violations committed by colleagues.

Behavior and Conduct:

Personnel must be friendly, polite, attentive, and respectful to citizens and colleagues. They must not display rudeness, harm the dignity or honor of individuals, or exert unwarranted psychological or physical pressure. During service, personnel's appearance should reflect the working environment and nature of duties, promoting respect for internal affairs bodies; uniforms should be clean and properly maintained.

Consumption of alcohol during service or while in uniform is strictly prohibited. Personnel may not use their official authority to advance the interests of political parties, public organizations, or private gain. Any abuse of official powers that harms citizens, society, or the legally protected interests of the state is strictly forbidden. Personnel who violate these rules and use their authority unlawfully will be held accountable in accordance with legislation.

Personnel are prohibited from performing or failing to perform their official duties in exchange for gifts or any form of material wealth from individuals or legal entities, or from using services provided by them. However, employees may accept gifts received in connection with individual service achievements if these are awarded in accordance with a decision of a state body, for accomplishments in competitions or contests, on public holidays, officially recognized dates, or other official events.

Personnel must also avoid situations that could cast doubt on their impartiality, independence, or integrity in interactions with citizens, and avoid any circumstances that could create favoritism, malice, or corruption.

During non-service hours, personnel are expected to:

- Adhere to socially recognized norms of morality and ethics, and respect national customs, values, and traditions;
- Avoid behaviors that could damage the reputation of internal affairs bodies;
- Refrain from extravagance, vanity, factionalism, indulgence, alcoholism, and other negative behaviors;
- Not discuss service-related information with family members, acquaintances, or individuals not involved in official work;
- Refrain from committing socially unacceptable acts.

During official business trips within Uzbekistan or abroad, personnel must perform assigned duties in accordance with legislation and the rules established by internal affairs normative documents. Service discipline in internal affairs bodies requires strict and unconditional adherence to the provisions of the Code. Discipline is based on each employee's full understanding of their service duties and a deep appreciation of personal responsibility for assigned tasks.

In addition to the main requirements of professional culture, personnel must fulfill the following obligations related to service discipline:

- Comply strictly with the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis, decrees, orders, and directives of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, resolutions and directives of the Cabinet of Ministers, and normative acts of the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

Obligations and Restrictions of Internal Affairs Personnel

Personnel of internal affairs bodies are required to:

- Faithfully uphold the oath of service, perform their duties unconditionally, and serve solely the interests of the people and the state;
- Serve diligently to protect citizens' rights and freedoms, lawful interests, the property of individuals and legal entities, the constitutional order, the rule of law, the security of individuals, society, and the state, as well as to prevent and counter violations of the law;
- Efficiently carry out their assigned duties and functional responsibilities;
- Safeguard entrusted service weapons, property, and equipment;
- Remain vigilant and strictly maintain state and service secrets;
- Assist colleagues in completing complex tasks;

- Follow rules regarding interpersonal relations, showing respect to supervisors and colleagues;
- Properly maintain and use service identification cards, strictly avoiding their use in situations unrelated to official duties, including not abusing one's position by displaying the service card;
- Continuously improve knowledge, professional skills, and legal culture;
- Conduct themselves appropriately during non-service hours, serving as a model in adhering to public order and moral standards.

Restrictions on Service with Relatives:

Personnel may not serve in the same internal affairs unit alongside close relatives or in-laws if such service would result in one being directly subordinate to the other.

Restrictions on Other Activities:

Personnel may not, outside of scientific, creative, or pedagogical work, engage in paid activities, entrepreneurial activities, establish or participate in business entities, hold managerial or administrative positions in business entities, participate in gambling or risk-based games, or use information and communication technologies for such activities. They may not seek citizenship of another country or a document granting permanent residence abroad, open or hold foreign bank accounts, own real estate or other property abroad, or pursue education abroad (except for internships or medical service purposes using accounts opened for these purposes).

Restrictions on Political and Religious Activities, and Responsibilities of Supervisors

Internal affairs personnel are prohibited from exercising their powers to serve the interests of political parties, other public associations, or their bodies (except when performing official duties), performing religious rites and ceremonies during service (except for childbirth, marriage, wedding, or funeral ceremonies), organizing religious rites and ceremonies in internal affairs buildings or on their premises, or storing religious materials and items (except when required for official duties).

Failure to comply with these restrictions may serve as grounds for an official service inspection. During the performance of official duties, a personnel member is directly subordinate to their immediate supervisor. Temporarily assigned supervisors are also considered direct superiors. The closest direct supervisor is regarded as the immediate superior.

The head of a unit within the internal affairs bodies is personally responsible for ensuring service discipline, effective implementation of moral-educational and training activities, and strict adherence to the Code by subordinates. The head must lead by example in demonstrating high professional skill, compliance with legal requirements, and loyalty to the oath of service, strengthening the sense of duty among personnel, encouraging initiative and dedication, and applying corrective measures in cases of service discipline violations.

The head must prevent personnel appointments or assignments based on kinship, local favoritism, personal connections, or other forms of loyalty. They must also eliminate manifestations of nepotism, favoritism, or other negative influences during the performance of duties. Adherence to the rules of professional culture and service discipline within internal affairs bodies ensures the development of high consciousness and thinking among personnel, the consistent conduct of moral-educational activities, and the application of appropriate incentives and disciplinary measures.

Incentives and Disciplinary Measures for Internal Affairs Personnel

Personnel may be rewarded through the following incentive measures:

- Expressing gratitude;
- Awarding valuable or commemorative gifts, or cash rewards;
- Awarding honorary certificates;
- Awarding departmental badges;
- Granting a special title ahead of schedule, or a special title one rank higher than the current position.

Additionally, as a form of incentive, previously imposed disciplinary penalties may be revoked ahead of schedule in accordance with established procedures.

In educational institutions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs (MIA), beyond the incentives listed above, cadets or students may also be rewarded by:

- Granting permission for unscheduled leave from the institution;
- Inclusion on the “Honor Board”;
- Sending a letter of appreciation to the cadet/student’s parents or residence;
- Awarding the “Jaloliddin Manguberdi” scholarship or recognition by the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Personnel may also be recommended for state honorary titles and awards of the Republic of Uzbekistan for exceptional service. However, regular salary, periodic bonuses, additional payments, allowances, and other cash remunerations are not considered incentive measures.

Disciplinary measures for personnel may include:

- Reprimand, severe reprimand;
- Fine not exceeding fifty percent of the monthly salary;
- Demotion in rank or special title;
- Removal from the current position;
- Detention in a guardhouse;
- Dismissal from service in the internal affairs bodies.

In MIA educational institutions, additional disciplinary measures for cadets or students may include:

- Assignment to unscheduled duty or household tasks for up to five days;
- Deprivation of the right to leave the institution for up to one month;
- Expulsion from the list of cadets or students.

However, such measures (unscheduled duty, household tasks, or temporary restriction from leaving the institution) are not applied to graduate-level students in MIA educational institutions.

Incentives and disciplinary measures are applied by supervisors within the limits of their authority. Issued incentives are announced via orders. Expressions of gratitude and permission for unscheduled leave can be announced either by order or verbally. The announcement of incentives may be made personally to the personnel, in front of a unit, or at an extended meeting or assembly.

At the time an incentive order is announced, as a rule, personnel are presented with an honorary certificate, valuable or commemorative gift, cash reward, or badge. The incentive must be recorded in the personnel’s personal file. The procedure for accounting incentive measures is determined by the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Application of disciplinary measures in internal affairs bodies

1. General Principles

- Disciplinary measures not provided for in the Code are prohibited.
- Only one disciplinary measure may be applied for a single offense.
- If multiple personnel violate service discipline, a separate disciplinary measure is

applied to each.

- Administrative violations cannot be punished with additional disciplinary measures.

- Application of disciplinary measures does not exempt personnel from criminal liability if the misconduct contains elements of a crime.

- Disciplinary actions must be justified and proportional to the severity of the offense and the degree of guilt.

2. Factors Considered When Imposing Disciplinary Measures

- Nature of the misconduct
- Circumstances under which it occurred
- Consequences of the act
- Previous behavior of the offender
- Length of service in the internal affairs body
- Attitude toward assigned duties

3. Minor Misconduct

- For minor offenses, the supervisor may limit the response to a verbal warning and guidance on preventing future incidents.

4. Disciplinary Councils

- To resolve conflicts and apply community influence on offenders, internal disciplinary councils may be established through election, operating according to regulations approved by the Minister of Internal Affairs.

5. Gross Violations of Service Discipline

- Includes the following behaviors:
 - Unjustified absence from the service location for more than three consecutive days
 - Being intoxicated by alcohol, drugs, or other substances at work
 - Acts endangering citizens' rights, safety, or health (if not criminal)
 - Breach of confidentiality rules (if not criminal)
 - Negligent or intentional damage, destruction, or loss of assigned weapons, property, or equipment (if not criminal)
 - Violation of rules during guard or convoy duties, leading to escape of detainees, loss of funds, property, or documents (if not criminal)

6. Evidence and Verification

- Intoxication claims are verified by medical examination. If the employee refuses, at least two witnesses or other persons' testimony is used.

7. Violation of Professional Culture Rules

- Gross breaches of professional ethics or disrespect in interpersonal relations with superiors and colleagues are considered damaging to the honor of internal affairs personnel.
- Minor domestic disputes not publicly displayed do not count as misconduct affecting honor.

8. Repeated Violations

- Regular violation of service discipline refers to multiple infractions while an existing disciplinary measure is in force.

9. Types of Disciplinary Measures

- Demotion in rank or removal from current position is applied when other disciplinary measures are insufficient.

- Detention in a guardhouse (gauptvahta) does not lead to dismissal from service.
 - Duration: Up to 10 days for enlisted personnel, sergeants, and junior officers; up to 5 days for senior officers.
 - Not applicable to female personnel.
- Procedure for imposing disciplinary measures on internal affairs personnel
1. Preliminary Explanation
 - Before imposing a disciplinary measure, the employee must provide a written explanation regarding the incident.
 - If the employee refuses to provide an explanation, an official report is drawn up.
 - Refusal to provide an explanation does not prevent the imposition of a disciplinary measure, nor does it justify a harsher penalty.
 2. Respect and Fairness
 - During the disciplinary process, the supervisor must not insult the employee's honor or act rudely.
 - Disciplinary action does not exempt the employee from compensating material damages caused by misconduct.
 3. Timeframe for Applying Disciplinary Measures
 - Must be applied within one month from the day the misconduct is reported to the supervisor.
 - If applied following a service inspection, the measure must be applied within 10 days after the inspection concludes, excluding periods when the employee is on leave or sick.
 - Disciplinary measures cannot be applied more than one year after the misconduct occurred.
 - For intoxicated employees, application of the measure and collection of explanations is postponed until the employee is sober.
 4. Announcement of Measures
 - Disciplinary measures are announced by order.
 - Measures such as extraordinary duty, up to five days of utility work, or restriction from leaving the educational institution for up to one month may be announced orally or in writing.
 - Announcement is made personally, in formation, or at an extended meeting.
 5. Source of Decision
 - Disciplinary measures are decided based on the recommendation of the disciplinary council and inspections conducted by the Ministry of Internal Affairs.
 6. Effect on Rewards and Promotions
 - Employees with active disciplinary measures cannot be considered for rewards, promotions, or higher ranks until the measure is lifted.
 - Filing a complaint does not suspend the execution of the disciplinary measure.
 7. Right to Appeal
 - Employees may appeal the disciplinary measure within one month to a superior or the personal security unit at the workplace.
 8. Duration of Disciplinary Measures
 - Disciplinary measures are time-limited and expire automatically after the following periods:
 - Reprimand: 3 months
 - Warning: 6 months

- Fine (up to 50% of salary): 9 months
 - Severe warning: 1 year
 - If multiple measures are applied within a single period, the expiration is calculated from the last imposed measure.
9. Documentation
- The disciplinary measure must be recorded in the employee's personal file.
 - Procedures for recording and tracking disciplinary measures are determined by the Minister of Internal Affairs.
10. Protection Against Abuse
- Employees have the right to submit written complaints against illegal or unfair actions of their supervisor to a higher authority or personal security unit.

If a complaint from an employee concern matters beyond the authority of the immediate superior, the higher-ranking official must forward the complaint to the competent authority within five days. A superior who persecutes a subordinate for filing a complaint regarding legal violations or unfair treatment is subject to disciplinary liability (provided their actions do not constitute a criminal offense).

Employees' complaints must be resolved within one month, while complaints not requiring additional investigation must be addressed promptly, but no later than 15 days from the date of receipt. Employees who deliberately submit false complaints are held accountable according to established procedures. Compliance with the provisions of the Code is monitored by the divisions responsible for moral-educational work and personnel management within the internal affairs bodies. Violations of the Code serve as a basis for accountability under applicable legislation.

At the same time, internal affairs bodies carry out their activities based on respect for citizens' rights, freedoms, and legal interests. Article 8 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" dated September 16, 2016, establishes that the internal affairs bodies must ensure the protection of citizens' rights, freedoms, and legal interests regardless of their gender, race, nationality, language, religion, beliefs, social origin, or social status, in accordance with the principle of respect for these rights and interests.

Any activity of internal affairs bodies that limits citizens' rights, freedoms, or legal interests must be immediately ceased if it is determined that the lawful objective has been achieved or could not be achieved without such limitation. Torture, violence, or any treatment that is cruel or degrading is strictly prohibited. Internal affairs officers are also required to prevent any intentional infliction of physical or moral suffering on citizens.

Each employee of the internal affairs bodies must perform their duties in accordance with these principles, ensuring that their behavior, conduct, and appearance comply with established standards. A technically skilled employee alone is insufficient; they must also demonstrate patriotism, national pride, and moral integrity. Employees who lack these qualities cannot achieve the organization's objectives effectively.

Conclusion

Therefore, it is a priority to educate the youth of Uzbekistan with a spirit of love for the Motherland, inspired by the courage of ancestors, and to instill a commitment to protect and cherish the homeland, remain vigilant to world events, act responsibly toward the people and the state, and foster loyalty, justice, honesty, and dedication to public service. This goal must be integrated into the education and training process as one of the most urgent tasks.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2023.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-6196 dated March 26, 2021, “On measures to elevate the activities of internal affairs bodies to a new quality level in ensuring public safety and combating crime.”
3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-5050, dated April 2, 2021 “On additional organizational measures to further improve the activities of internal affairs bodies in ensuring public safety and combating Crime.”
4. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-5040, dated March 26, 2021 “On measures to fundamentally improve the system of moral and educational work.”
5. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-10, dated January 20, 2023 “On additional measures to transform internal affairs Bodies into a people-oriented professional structure and promote closer cooperation with the population.”